

57-66 d (Fig. 1). A female can lay as many as 87 eggs. Mean daily oviposition is shown in Figure 2. Mortality was highest at the 3d nymphal stage.

The species requires constantly flowing water, which is why it has low populations in ricefields. It also exhibits cannibalism. □

Integrated pest management – weeds

Weeds in direct seeded ricefields of Thanjavur District, Tamil Nadu

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Weeds are a more serious problem in dry seeded rice than in wet seeded rice culture. We assessed weed species in direct seeded (dry seeded) rice 60 d after sowing in three cropping seasons: kuruvai (Jun-Jul to Sep-Oct) and thaladi (Sep-Oct to Feb-Mar) in double crop wetlands and samba (Aug-Sep to Jan-Feb) in single crop wetlands.

The major graminaceous weeds were *Echinochloa colona*, *E. crus-galli*, and *Chloris barbata*. The common Cyperaceae were *Cyperus rotundus*, *C. iria*, and *Fimbristylis miliacea*. Of nine families of dicots present, Onagraceae, Marsileaceae, and Asteraceae were important.

Weed density was highest during the samba season because of favorable moisture and climatic conditions (see table). Weed flora during kuruvai consisted of nearly equal densities of monocots and dicots. During thaladi and samba, monocots were dominant.

Irrespective of season, among the monocots *E. colona* was the major species (50-81%). *C. rotundus* (50-65%) dominated the sedges and *Ludwigia adscendens* and *Marsilea quadrifolia* (30-50%) dominated the broadleaf weeds. □

Fig. 1. Age-specific survival rate (lx) of the water strider *L. fossarum*, constructed using a life-table analysis, IRR, 1989. N = nymphal stage; X = 60.25 ± 1.18 .

Fig. 2. Average daily oviposition of water strider *L. fossarum*. IRR, 1989;

Weed density in direct seeded rice, Tamil Nadu, India.

Weed	Kuruvai		Thaladi		Samba	
	Density (no./m ²)	Relative density (%)	Density/m	Relative density (%)	Density/m	Relative density (%)
<i>Echinochloa colona</i> (L.) Link	82	32.1	68	34.3	183	55.0
<i>E. crus-galli</i> (L.) P. Beauv.	8	3.1	28	14.1	18	5.4
<i>Chloris barbata</i> Sw.	12	4.7	22	11.2	14	4.2
Others	3	1.2	21	10.6	12	3.6
Total grasses	105	41.3	139	70.2	227	68.2
<i>Cyperus rotundus</i> L.	16	6.3	8	4.0	20	6.0
<i>C. iria</i> L.	6	2.4	4	2.0	4	1.2
<i>Fimbristylis miliacea</i> (L.) Vahl	4	1.6	2	1.0	4	1.2
Others	5	2.0	3	1.6	5	1.5
Total sedges	31	12.2	17	8.6	33	9.9
<i>Ludwigia adscendens</i> (L.) Hara	42	16.5	12	6.2	38	11.4
<i>Marsilea quadrifolia</i> L.	26	10.2	21	10.6	16	4.8
<i>Eclipta alba</i> (L.) Hassk.	18	7.2	4	2.0	9	2.7
Others	32	12.6	5	2.5	10	3.0
Total broadleaf weeds	118	46.5	42	21.2	73	21.9
Total weeds	254	100.0	198	100.0	333	100.0